

EXISTENCE OF EARLY HUMAN LIFE, UNVEILING ANCIENT ROCK ART LANDSCAPES IN TWO SIGNIFICANT VALLEYS NAMELY THE GREAT ANISUN VALLEY AND ANISUN VALLEY OF VERVE CLOSE TO KUNUKUNTLA IN OWK MANDAL

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ABSTRACT :

This research study discusses the ancient rock paintings discovered in the Great AniSun Valley and the AniSun Valley of Verve in the Erramala forest range nearby two significant living habitats, Kunukuntla and Uppalapadu in Owk mandal, Nandyal district, which is a subsection of the Kurnool group of Cuddapah supergroup. This research paper also presents an overview of the evolution of early human life and rock art in the two significant valleys that contain 92 rock shelters and more than 2300 rock paintings. It adds to the growing body of knowledge about Indian prehistoric art, providing a comprehensive exploration of its cultural history and phenomenology. The findings of this places provide as fine examples of the prehistoric humans efforts to create the ideal living environment, particularly painted figures on the surface of quartzite boulders, the depiction of bison, deer, wild boar, lizard, snake, salt water crocodile, butterfly, turtle, buffalo, donkey, horse, fish, rabbit, ox, frog, spider, scorpion, pangolin, centipede and the representation of a hunting scene by early humans.

KEYWORDS : Rock Art, Great AniSun Valley, India, Mesolithic, AniSun Valley of Verve, Paintings.

INTRODUCTION :

Rock art is a witness of existence of early human life and their living life style, prehistoric man showcased their potential skill in rock paintings. In early times rock art is used as a communication tool and to express their thoughts and feelings. Rock paintings are preserved for longer duration than spoken and gestural communication systems. Prehistoric human understood the importance of this concept of graphical representation. The graphical representation of rock art includes five different types, one is pictographs (drawings and paintings depicted on rock) second is petroglyphs (an image made

by incising, picking, carving, or scratching a portion of a rock surface) third is engravings (a drawing made by sharp tool to decorate stone surfaces with painting) fourth is petroforms (shapes or pattern placed in the open ground from large stones) fifth is geoglyphs (ground or land drawings).

Early pictorial representations include representations of faunal and human, as well as diamond shapes (**Figure 27**) and geometrical symbols. Many Indian researchers carried out amazing work in the early quarter of the century. Many researchers carried out research to date the rock art and their artifacts and some researchers focused on faunal remains but very few researchers focused on the prehistoric man environmental aspects and ideal place for living. While researching this subject, author1 (Avula Anil Kumar) identified two locations (**Figure 1, Figure 3**) that met the early human life requirements as potential locations for the possibility of prehistoric human life. The Great AniSun Valley (**Figure 3**) and AniSun Valley of Verve (**Figure 1**), the two locations chosen for the study, provided evidence of early human life and their rock art landscapes. The two valleys consist of rock arts close to Kunukuntla and Uppalapadu of Owk mandal in Nandyal district was discovered by **Avula Anil Kumar** (author1) and his team members (author 2,3,4,5) (**Figure 25**) during this research.

Prehistoric rock art in Indian sub-continent are found across the length (from northern himalayan ranges to southern tip of kanyakumari) and the breadth (from east to west) of the country. This is the reason, in December 2004, an International Rock Art Congress was established in Agra (Uttar Pradesh), south part of New Delhi. Many scientists and research scholars contributed their life in finding new rock art sites in India. Here, We call Padmasree Dr Vishnu Wakankar as the “Father of Indian Rock Art” for his extraordinary contributions in finding the early rock art sites in India. His greatest discoveries including the Bhimbetka rock art site in 1957 which comes under south-east region of Bhopal. In 2003, UNESCO added the Bhimbetka rock art paintings on its list of cultural heritage. Many rock art sites in India was discovered by many archaeologists, but Archibald Carlleyle who discovered the first rock art paintings in the world in 1867-68 was made in India at (Vindhya, Mirzapur District, Uttar Pradesh) but his discoveries was not published during that period. Twelve years prior to the discovery of Altamira in Northern Spain, this discovery was made. There are some other few eminent scholars who contributed in finding Indian rock art paintings. Mostly they focused on northern and central part of India (Brooks 1976), Cockburn (1899), A Sundara(1967), P Rajendran (1985), Neumayer (1983,1993), Pandey (1992), Pradhan (2001), Mathpal (1984), Chakravarty (1984), D.W. Robinson (2008) at south Indian part of Bellary district in Karnataka. James Blinkhorn (2010) and N Chandramouli (2002) surveyed and recorded rock paintings in Kurnool District and Andhra Pradesh.

Some of the important rock art sites in northern India are Dras, Nurla, Kargil, Mulbekh, leh (UT of Ladakh), Almora in Uttarakhand, Bhalldharja, Bjayagarh, Kauva, Hathvani, Khoh, Likhunia, Lakhma, mukhadari, Varanasi, Prayagraj, Agra and Ganga-Yamuna Doab area of Utterpradesh. There're some important rock art sites in southern India from Kupgal, Badami, Maski, Piklihal, Tekkalakota in Karnataka, Dupadugattu in Telangana. Boulders were used as rock shelters by prehistoric human and the rock art was found in that shelters and that can be noticed at Budagavi, Chintakunta, Ketavaram, Akkampalli of Sanjamala mandal, Katikavanikunta, Jwalapuram of Banaganapalli mandal in Kurnool district, Idupulapaya (very close to famous IIIT Rk Valley Campus) of Vempalli mandal in Kadapa district. Naidupalli (only the rock art site that was found in costal region and shale formations in Andhra Pradesh) in Prakasam district of Andhra Pradesh, Alambadi and Padiyandal in Tamilnadu, Edakkal and Ezuthupara in Kerala. The Great AniSun Valley and AniSun Valley of Verve forms under the part of the Purana Basin in Cuddapah super group of Kurnool group.

Location of two valleys near Kunukuntla :

The two rock art site valleys are situated close to Kunukuntla village. The gram panchayat of Kunukuntla, which has a population of 2,389 and around 562 homes, is located 10 kilometers west from the sub-district headquarters Owk. The total geographical area of Kunukuntla gram panchayat is 5668 hectares. Kurnool district is recognized as one of the significant landmark with the ancient archaeological rock art sites ranging from Paleolithic period to Megalithic period. Kunukuntla is a tiny meseta that is part of the Purana Basin of Cuddapah basin. This meseta's faulting activity in this region resulted in the formation of 17 minor and major valleys, including 4 major and 13 minor ones.

From a geological perspective, the quartzite formation at Kunukuntla landscape is known as Pinnacled Quartzite, Paniam Quartzite, or Plateau Quartzite. These large quartzite boulders are formed when pure quartz sandstone is compressed and this is typically brought on by tectonic compression. Prehistoric humans used these boulders as their shelters. It was noticed during this research that every location featuring boulders provided testimony of early humans existence and their rock art. In the same way the two valleys that containing boulders showed the presence of prehistoric human and their rock art paintings within these rock shelters. This research was focused on two adjacent valleys of the Great AniSun Valley and

AniSun Valley of Verve and better understanding of how sites are distributed across the landscape and how surface archaeology relates to them.

Location of Locality1 (Great AniSun Valley) :

Location of the locality1 (**Figure 3**) is named as the Great AniSun Valley by the author of this research paper. Locality1 comes under Kunukuntla gram panchayat in Owk mandal. Locality1 is 1.2kms away from nearby hamlet village called Isranaik thanda and 2.6kms away from the famous kambagiri temple. The approximate length of the locality1 (Great AniSun Valley) is 4.9kms with the width ranging in between 100-160mtrs.

Location of Locality2 (AniSun Valley of Verve) :

Location of the locality2 (**Figure 1**) is named as AniSun Valley of Verve by the author of this research paper. Locality2 comes under Kunukuntla gram panchayat in Owk mandal. Locality2 is 1.4kms away from Kunukuntla village. Locality2 is situated adjacent and parallel to the locality1 with a distance of 2.1kms. The approximate length of the locality2 (AniSun Valley of Verve) is 4.5kms with the width ranging in between 50-100mtrs.

Geological and Geographical features of this region :

According to geological classification, the two locations that have revealed evidence of ancient humans and their rock art paintings belongs to the Cuddapah Supergroup of the Kurnool group (**Figure 2**) in peninsular India. Kurnool group is considered as youngest group of the Cuddapah Supergroup and younger than 1140Ma; however, the minimum and maximum age for shales of the Kurnool Group is proposed as 500 Ma (K/Ar) and 980 Ma (Rb/Sr) respectively [4]. The Kurnool transitional zone represented by thin, wavy bedded to rippled, medium grained quartzite distinguishes the transitional zone from the underlying Owk Shale. The majority of the Paniam Quartzite is made up of extremely finely sorted quartz arenite. This basin is divided into six formations that are : Banaganapalli Quartzite is the lowermost formation, Narji, Owk Shale, Koilakuntla, Paniam Quartzite and Nandyal is the uppermost formation [2]. Geographically the two locality's are situated in the Erramala region in the form of quartzite meseta with 17 minor and major valleys. Kunukuntla panchyat region is measured about 70 sq.km. Only rocky mountains with quartzite can be found here, which led to intense heat waves in the summer because of the high levels of direct sunlight reflection. Rainwater from all major and minor valleys will flow towards the eastern side of the meseta during the spring rainy season, and it will accumulate in a large, naturally formed earthen reservoir at Owk.

The Rock Art landscape of Locality1 & Locality2 :

The Rock Art Site of Locality1 (Great AniSun Valley) :

The Great AniSun Valley is steeply sloped but relatively wide and runs along an east-west axis. Fourteen rock shelters with rock art paintings (**Figure 3**) have been found on the overhangs of the quartzite boulders in the valley. Most of the rock art was in Red colour and all of the rock shelters with rock art is on the lower region of the valley. The archaeological rock art research by the authors was started at the coordinates 15°11'39.4" N and 77°58'19.9"E and ended the research at the coordinates 15°11'54.3"N and 78°00'33.2"E. Rock shelters without rock art was noticed in few shelters in this valley.

The Rock Art Site of Locality2 (AniSun Valley of Verve) :

AniSun Valley of Verve is an up-lowland valley that cuts through the paniam quartzite, it runs on a east west axis and lies adjacent and parallel to the locality1. Twenty seven rock shelters with rock art have been found on the quartzite boulders in the valley. This valley's rock art uses the colours red, white, and black, while red being the most used colour in several rock shelters. The systematic research by the authors started at the coordinates 15°11'15.3"N and 78°01'30.6"E and ended at the coordinates 15°10'18.0"N and 77°59'18.6"E. Fifty two rock shelters recorded no rock art but recorded striated marks on the surfaces of the rock shelters and few rock shelters recorded with totally faded dull rock art in the valley.

General Traits of Locality1 & Locality2 rock art :

Locality1 (Great AniSun Valley) :

The rock art that was found in locality1 represents the figures of an anthropoids or similar to human images, antelopes and figures of fauna, hunting scenes (**Figure 4**), geometrical signs and diamond like structured figures (**Figure 28**). Most of the rock art in locality1 was in red colour and 96% of the red colour paint was made by using hematite and red ochre and rest 4% of white paintings was made by using kaolin clay, calcium carbonate and calcium oxide. The phases of rock art in different periods can be identified by usage of various colours, depiction of images from faded thin red colour to thick red colour. The stylistic features the rock paintings in locality1 shows the early phase of Mesolithic art. Most of the rock art was in motifs and geometric patterns, few with decorative body and x-ray lines.

Locality2 (AniSun Valley of Verve) :

The rock art paintings in locality2 including depiction of an antelope in many rock shelters, joyful human representation (**Figure 15**), aquatic animals and mostly abstract and geometrical signs. Locality2 reveals the best ideal place for living in three different phases by the prehistoric human. In rock shelter4 authors noticed three different stylistic art with red, white and black colors paintings this reveals that the same rock shelter was reused in three successive human phases, from the prehistoric human to the Iron age. Rock shelter1 and rock shelter15 in locality 2 also exhibit rock art in the form of petroglyphs and engravings. 85% of the rock art found in locality 2 was painted in red; hematite and red ochre are used to produce red paintings; 12% was discovered to be painted in white; kaolin clay, calcium carbonate, and calcium oxide were used to produce white paintings; and 3% was discovered to be painted in black; charcoal is used to produce black paintings. According to the rock art's usage of three different colours and its various stylistic features, locality2 provided hospitality to the prehistoric man of Mesolithic and Neolithic eras. The shelters they used were large quartzite rocks and rock shelter25 in locality2 (**Figure 35**) is determined to be one of the largest gathering and habitation site of prehistoric human with the length of 60m on both the sides (front to front). Most of the rock art is complex in non-figurative patterns with dot like decorations and abstract signs. Rock shelter3 is recorded highest number of paintings in locality2 (**Figure 1**) with 127 rock paintings is such a highest number of images recorded at single rock shelter in making it the most numerous rock shelter overall when compared to the rock art in the two valleys and rock shelter4 recorded 105 paintings making second highest painting site recorded at single place.

Environmental Features of the region :

Early humans wished to reside in environments that gave them access to resources they needed to survive throughout the life. The specific habitats varied depending on the region and local environmental conditions. Both localities 1 and 2 are considered to have the best environmental conditions for the habitation of early humans. The two valleys located in centre of the meseta formation. The two locality's are river valleys with many water lakes and green wet grasslands across the length of the valleys. Rock shelters with rock art was found throughout the length of the river valleys. These river valleys provided abundance of resources to survive. Prehistoric humans settled in these two river valleys for taking advantage of freshwater availability throughout the year for drinking, fishing and transportation. The two locality's also supported a variety of plants and animal life, making them favourable for hunting and gathering. Large, naturally formed rocks with hundreds of quartzite boulders that prehistoric humans used as shelter during the Paleolithic and Mesolithic eras have been found in both valleys, attracting them to settle there. Two river valleys contain a variety of fruit trees, including mango, tamarind, black plum, plums, swimming fruits etc, in addition, both valleys contain some other plants that are usual in our surroundings, such as neem, beech, banyan, and prosopis juliflora trees. The two valleys are habitat to a variety of wild animals especially deer (**Figure 13**), wild boar, rabbit (**Figure 5**) and more, that ancient humans used to hunt for food. The three basic necessities of early humans were food, water, and shelter. According to these needs, the Great AniSun Valley (**Figure 3**) and the AniSun Valley of Verve (**Figure 1**) provided our ancestors with water, food, and shelter to survive and as a result, there is rock art in both valleys indicating their existence.

Pictographs from Locality1 (Great AniSun Valley) rock shelters :

The pictographs that are found in locality1 are representation of humans, hunting scenes and most of the animal images painted here are deer, wild boar and rabbit, surprisingly these animals are hunted for food by the prehistoric humans. There are numerous anthropoids painted with two hands and two legs, but in rock shelter 2, it was observed that a human-like figure with two hands and legs (**Figure 4**) that resembled fibrous root system was using an arrow to hunt an unknown animal. Depiction of three humans climbing ladder like structure found at rock shelter3 on a large quartzite boulder. In rock

shelter6 noticed that the images of two humans standing side by side (**Figure 6**), motifs, some fauna images like centipede (**Figure 7**), tortoise, deer, horse, abstract and non-figurative images. Representation of a herbivorous animal- a rabbit (**Figure 5**) (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) standing on his two legs and another two legs are upraised and depiction of a wild boar, geometrical shapes and vessel liked image was identified at rock shelter13. Along with the fauna and geometrical shapes, representation of a language symbols (**Figure 32**) found at this site. Rock shelter13 is only the site featuring with language symbols found in this valley.

Pictographs, Petroglyph and Engraving from Locality2 (AniSun Valley of Verve) rock shelters :

The pictographs that are identified in locality2 are mostly fauna and aquatic animal representations like ox, buffalo, donkey, deer, pangolin, salt water crocodile, fish, frog etc. The rock shelter1 has a petroglyph of a bull with long horns and a tail of average size. The location of the site is in a productive farming area with lush grassland, farming practices were started during the end stage of Mesolithic period and starting stage of Neolithic period. Perhaps the petroglyph of bull (**Figure 22**) shows that early farming methods are done by bull by the prehistoric humans at this site. According to the stylistic art work and art site the petroglyph belongs to Neolithic period. A fish (**Figure 28**), diamond shaped chain (**Figure 27**), and some abstract symbols are found in rock shelter3. Early humans hunted fish the most and made it one of their favourite aquatic foods; it is abundantly available in locality2 because it is a river valley. Accordingly, a fish's representation describes the abundance of fish at this locality and their preferred food source.

In rock shelter4, noticed three different colour paintings such as red, white and black. The shelter was used for the first time in Mesolithic period according to the red colour paintings like scorpion (**Figure 34**), spider (**Figure 36**) and unknown animal body decorated with abstract patterns and the same rock shelter was reused in Neolithic/ Iron age by the prehistoric human according to the white colour paintings such as lizards (**Figure 16**) and language symbols. At a rock shelter13, there are paintings of a knife weapon tool, a cross symbol (**Figure 19**), frogs (**Figure 26**), and a happy human figure (**Figure 15**) stretching out his two arms. A sharp sword-like weapon (**Figure 23**) was identified in rock shelter12. It's interesting that the two images of weapon tools can be found next to each other in a rock shelter. Representation of six butterflies in a row (**Figure 24**), an animal without a head whose body was painted with geometric symbols, and a painting of a rushing deer (**Figure 10**) whose body was covered in dotted straight lines and had a longer tail than usual were additional notable paintings from rock shelter22. A painting of a python (**Figure 11**), a member of the reptile family, measuring around 1.2 meters long, was discovered in rock shelter23. In rock shelter24, images of donkey (**Figure 17**) and zebra liked animal was found. Along with an engraving of a square-shaped image (**Figure 30**) and a straight line passing through the middle of a square shape, a snake-like reptile (**Figure 18**) with curves of about 1 m in length was also discovered in a rock shelter27. Compared to both valleys, only rock shelter23 has provided evidence of rock art by engraving technique. In rock shelter18 noticed the representation of pangolin (**Figure 20**) which is a mammal, lizard and salt water crocodile (**Figure 21**) belongs to reptile and moose liked animal. Most importantly, it should be highlighted that pangolin image drawn by prehistoric people are now on the International Union for the Conservation of Nature's endangered species list. In rock shelter17, depiction of a buffalo (**Figure 12**), deer (**Figure 13**) and human hand prints (**Figure 14**) are identified.

Dating of rock art paintings from Locality1 & Locality2 :

Determining the age of rock art can be a complex process that requires careful examinations and analysis of various factors in rock art research. Most of the rock art would date basis on rock art style and characteristics, associated archaeological evidences, weathering layer on the surfaces of rock art and cross dating techniques. In this research the authors followed some parameters like rock art style, cross checking with other rock art sites, paintings used etc, to date the rock art. According to the previously said criterion, rock art that found in both two valleys dated to Mesolithic period. Based on style and similarity criteria, 94% of the rock art is from Mesolithic period and rest 6% of the rock art is from Neolithic and Iron age. Mesolithic tradition was seen in all rock paintings from locality1 and locality2.

DISCUSSION :

The two rock art site valleys close to kunukuntla represented many geometrical and abstract signs that are very harder to decode. Early humans depicted graphical language symbols representation in locality1 rock shelter13 (**Figure 32**). The symbols are decoded in some way by comparison with other symbols found at different rock art sites throughout the world and the meaning of the language symbol found at locality1 rock shelter13 is supplication to their God, and must be a deeper devotional notion. Got the evidence of existence of pangolin (**Figure 20**) at this region in south India. Indian pangolins are

now listed as endangered species. The representation of pangolin is may be one of their eaten food by the prehistoric man. Noticed hunting scenes from both two locality's in more times by the prehistoric human.

The use of arrows to chase an animal and the creation of animal traps demonstrate how skill full early humans hunted for food. The representation of deer (**Figure 13**), fish (**Figure 28**) and antelopes in many rock shelters at both the valleys reveals the abundance availability and easy to hunt for their favourite meals and hence favourite and most liked species among many animals. Various animal pictographs belong to different families were discovered in two valleys like reptiles, amphibians, mammals, aquatic animals and representation of six butterflies in a row at rockshelter22 locality2. The depiction of butterflies (**Figure 24**) shows seasonal insect that can be seen in monsoon and post monsoon times during rains. Additionally, butterflies are very beautiful insects that admired early humans to depict. The depiction of antelopes, rabbit (**Figure 5**), buffalo (**Figure 12**) and ox represents the environmental conditions in two locality's and that shows availability of grasslands and deciduous land combined environment. In rock shelter25 at locality2 is found largest gathering and habitation site by the prehistoric human. Social organization in early Mesolithic period likely had social structures and organized themselves in a small group gathering. Cooperative among group members was crucial for survival, as they shared tasks like hunting for food, gathering and childcare.

Rock art is continued for many years starting from Paleolithic period to recent Megalithic period. Most of the rock art in Andhra Pradesh was found in purana basin. Many rock art sites were discovered in Kurnool region. Kurnool group of rock art site is considered as south India's most heritage. It recognized to be a Indian mode of graphical representation by early human origins that unites numerous ethnic groups on the subcontinent, a mode of common cultural legacy that is distinctly 'Indian' in nature. Since India is connected with various historical eras hence more research is needed to understand.

Figures :

Figure 1 : Google Map showing Rock Shelter sites in Locality2 – AniSun Valley of Verve

Figure 2 : Geological Map of Kurnool group of Cuddapah super group and Rock art site of Great AniSun Valley and AniSun Valley of Verve

Figure 3 : Google Map showing Rock Shelter Sites of Locality1 – The Great AniSun Valley

Figure 4 : Hunting scene from rock shelter2, Locality1

Figure 5 : Representation of a rabbit standing on two legs with two upraised legs at rock shelter13, Locality1

Figure 6 : Depiction of Humans at rock shelter6, Locality1

Figure 7 : Representation of a Centepede from rock shelter6, Locality1

Figure 8 : Depiction of Horse and Cow at rock shelter6, Locality1

Figure 9 : Representation of an antelope at rock shelter22, Locality2

Figure 10 : Depiction of a rushing deer with dotted straight lines in the body at rock shelter23, Locality2

Figure 11 : Representation of a python at rock shelter23, Locality2

Figure 12 : Painting of a long horned buffalo found at rock shelter18, Locality2

Figure 13 : Depiction of a long horned deer at rock shelter18, Locality2

Figure 14 : Depiction of a Human Hand Print discovered at rock shelter18, Locality2

Figure 15 : Representation of a Joyous Human stretched his two arms at rock shelter13, Locality2

Figure 16 : Depiction of five, six legged lizards with white paint at rock shelter4, Locality2

Figure 17 : Painting of a Donkey at rock shelter24, Locality2

Figure 18 : Depiction of a Snake liked animal measured 1m at rock shelter27, Locality2

Figure 19 : Representation of a Knife and Cross at rock shelter13, Locality2

Figure 20 : Image of an Endangered Species – Pangolin at rock shelter20, Locality2

Figure 21 : Depiction of a Lizard and salt water crocodile at rock shelter20, Locality2

Figure 22 : Petroglyph of a long horned Bison with average sized tail at rock shelter2, Locality2

Figure 23 : Representation of Weapon Tool – Sword at rock shelter11, Locality2

Figure 24 : Depiction of Butterflies in a row at rock shelter18, Locality2

Figure 25 : Authors researching for rock arts of three different paints used at rock shelter3, Locality2

Figure 26 : Representation of a Jumping Frog at rock shelter13, Locality2

Figure 27 : Depiction of Diamond structured chain at rock shelter3, Locality2

Figure 28 : Painting of aquatic animal – Fishes at rock shelter3, Locality2

Figure 30 : Engraving on a rock surface found at rock shelter27, Locality2

Figure 31 : Author1 and Author5 researching rock art at rock shelter13, Locality1

Figure 32 : Representation of a Language Symbols at rock shelter13, Locality1

Figure 33 : Authors at rock shelter6, Locality1

Figure 34 : Representation of a Scorpion at rock shelter3, Locality2

Figure 35 : Site of the biggest Gathering and Habitation shelter by Prehistoric Human in Locality2

Original

Digital Art on Original Art

Figure 36 : Depiction of a Spider at rock shelter3, Locality2

Figure 37 : Naturally formed rock shelter in between two large Quarzite boulder at rock shelter12, Locality2

Figure 38 : Author1 showing round two side opened naturally formed rock shelter at Locality1

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